

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC STATUS OF SERICULTURE GROWERS IN BEED DISTRICT OF MARATHWADA REGION

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Abstract:

The current investigation primarily delves into the Socio-Economic status of sericulture growers in mulberry and cocoon production. Sericulture, is a rural agro-cottage industry which can be adopted by the weaker sections of the society. Sericulture is one the farming approach in ensuring the farmer's regular income and can helps them in generating the employment level. Thus it play an indispensable role for the poor sections of the society in improving their standard of living. Thus being a potential farming enterprise and having a great opportunity of employment generation, sericulture enterprise can acts as an appropriate avenues for socio-economic development of rural population. For selecting districts, tehsils, villages, and sericulture growers for the study a multistage sampling design was employed. In the Marathwada region, specifically, Beed district was purposively chosen on the basis of availability of area under Sericulture production from the Marathwada region.. From Beed district two tehsils and from each tehsil four villages were then selected, resulting in a total of 8 villages with 80 sample respondents. The study utilized descriptive statistics to study the socio-economic status of sericulture growers. The paper found that most of the sericulture growers were found to be of middle age group, married, had education up to secondary level, medium size of family, small farmers, belonged to general category, had nuclear family, kachcha type of house, growing mulberry on medium type of soil, V1 variety of mulberry and CSR Double hybrid type of cocoon species. The proportionate area under mulberry cultivation was 0.62 ha i.e. 29.30 per cent to gross cropped area.

Keywords: sericulture, Mulberry, cocoons production, agro-cottage industry, potential farming enterprise, income and employment, socio-economic development.

Introduction

India is an agriculture dominating country. About more than 60 per cent of population depends on the agriculture. Sericulture is a highly labour intensive and a rural agro-based industry. Large number of small and marginal land holders are predominant in India who wholly depend on agriculture. The word "sericulture" has been derived from word "su" (si) which means silk. Sericulture is whole practice comprising of mulberry cultivation and rearing of silkworm. Sericulture can be done in rural area with it's economical and environmental sustainable practices that helps the farmers in generating employment level at rural area with ensuring a regular income to the small and marginal farmers, so that it helps in checking the problem of migration from rural to the urban areas. Especially, women contributes the major part while conducting the several skilled practices; both in the on farm and off farm activities i.e. from mulberry cultivation to the harvesting of cocoon. Sericulture is extremely competitive and capital-intensive enterprise which is widely practice dall over India in rural and semi-urban area (Yadav, 2008). Silk is a fibroin made of proteins secreted in the fluid state as single filament by a caterpillar, popularly known as 'silkworm'. These silkworms feed on the selected food plants and spin cocoons as a 'protective shell' to perpetuate the life.

Silk has some special characteristics like natural sheen and inherent affinity for dyes, light weight, soft touch and high in durability that makes it more qualitative in nature. Because of these unique characteristics silk is termed as "Queen of Textiles". Cultivation of mulberry plants is known as Moriculture. Around 20 species of mulberry are available, of which four are common: *Morus alba*, *M.indica*, *M.serrata*, and *M.latifolia*. The origin of silk was first found in the country of china, in the world. Globally, China ranks first followed by India in the production of silk. The major silk producing states in the country are Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Assam and Bodoland, West Bengal, Jharkhand and Tamil Nadu. India is the only country of producing all the five known commercial types of silk viz., Mulberry, Tropical Tasar, Oak Tasar, Eri and Muga silk. India is the second largest producer of silk in world. Among all the types Mulberry contributed for 73.97 %, (25,818 MT), Tasar 4.20 % (1,466 MT), Eri 21.10 % (7,364 MT) and Muga 0.73 % (255 MT) of the

total raw silk production of 34,903 MT. (Central Silk Board, annual report 2023)

The sericulture is considered as lower investment with higher return within the short gestation period. In the agriculture sector, sericulture is the only cash crop that gives returns within 30 days (Yadav 2013). Sericulture provides income and employment to the whole family including women, which is a household activity. Women contributed about 60 per cent to the sericulture workforce (Central Silk Board, Benguluru, 2022). The employment generation in silk industry in the country is 8.8 million persons in 2021- 22 compared to 8.7 million persons in 2020-21, indicating an increase of 1.1 per cent.(Central Silk Board, annual report 2023) By taking into account all the aspects, the objective of this investigation is study the socio-economic status of sericulture growers.

Methodology:

Multistage sampling design was adopted in selection of district, tehsils, villages and ultimate sericulture growers. The study area pertains to Marathwada region of Maharashtra state. In the first stage, Beed district purposively selected on the basis of availability of area under Sericulture production from the Marathwada region. On the basis of area under sericulture production, tehsils were purposively selected for the present study. In second stage, two tehsils of each selected districts were selected i.e. from Beed : Dharur and Beed, Thus, total two tehsils were selected based on large number of sericulture growers. The random selection method was adopted in selection of villages. In the third stage from each selected Tehsils, four villages were selected randomly, on the basis of highest area under sericulture production. Sericulture growers were selected by using random selection method. In the fourth stage 10 sericulture growers were randomly selected from each selected villages. Thus from 8 villages, 80 growers were selected. The study was based on the primary data. Primary data required for the present study were collected with the help of pre tested and well-structured schedule with an intensive visits at farm level through personal interviews. The data were collected during the period 2022-2023. Simple tabular analysis was employed to study the Socio-economic status of sericulture growers.

Results and Discussion

The socio-economic status of the farmers is considered as the significant parameter in order to determine the farmers standard of living, level of adoption of new technology, acknowledge the new things which also takes into account the various factors such as age of farmer, level of education, level of occupation, family size, family type, experience etc., that influences the adoption level as well as financial condition of farmers. The salient findings of the study have been presented as follows:

Table 1: Distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of age

Districts	Age			Grand Total
	Young (20-35 years)	Middle (36-60 years)	Old (> 60 years)	
Beed	9 (11.25)	64 (80.00)	7 (8.75)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

It was observed from the table, that the Beed district shows the large number of sample farmers i.e. 64 (80.00 per cent) were belonged to middle age group followed by young age 9 (11.25 per cent) sericulture growers and old age group 7 (8.75 per cent) sericulture growers.

The results of the study, represents that most of the farmers were observed in between middle age group followed by old and young age group. The majority of the farmers having middle age group was found to be in the Beed district about 80 per cent, The conclusion of the study were in relevance with the findings of Yadav (2013).

Table 2: Distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of level of education

Districts	Education Level							Grand Total
	Illiterate	Primary	Secondary	Higher Secondary	Graduate	Post Graduate	Other	
Beed	7 (8.75)	16 (20.00)	24 (30.00)	16 (20.00)	11 (13.75)	1 (1.25)	5 (6.25)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

It was found that, the Beed district showed the large number of sample farmers were educated up to secondary 24 (30.00 per cent) followed by other people those were having primary education 16 (20.00 per cent), and were educated up to higher secondary 16 (20.00 per cent), 11 (13.75 per cent) sericulture growers were graduated, 7 (8.75 per cent) farmers were illiterate, 5 (6.25 per cent) farmers were having Agriculture diploma, Veterinary diploma etc. whereas only 1 (1.25 per cent) was post graduated farmer.

It was observed that majority of sericulture farmers are having primary to secondary level of education, as sericulture is technically oriented enterprise, where there is need to have higher education for

Table 3: Distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of occupational level

Districts	Occupational Level				Grand Total
	Agriculture	Agriculture +Business	Agriculture +Service	Agriculture +Other	
Beed	71 (88.75)	2 (2.50)	5 (6.25)	2 (2.50)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

In the Beed district, the study revealed that a significant number of sericulture growers 71 (88.75 per cent) were involved in agriculture followed by the farmers who were involved in agriculture along with service were 5 (6.25 per cent), 2 (2.50 per cent) were working both in agriculture and business and 2 (2.50 per cent) other farmers were observed in agriculture and other occupation.

Sericulture growers' distribution on the basis of Family Size

The distribution of sericulture growers as per the family size across the Beed district is presented in Table 4. In addition to this the grand total shows the total number of farmers selected in district. The data

Table 4: Distribution of sericulture farmer on the basis of family size

Districts	Family Size			Grand Total
	Small (<3 members)	Medium (4-5 members)	Large (>5 members)	
Beed	9 (11.25)	47 (58.75)	24 (30.00)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

Sericulture growers distribution according to the age

The distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of age is presented in Table 1. On the availability of the data of sericulture growers, the age group was categorized into young (20-35), middle (35-60) and old (>60) years. The grand total shows that the district was having 80 sericulture growers in the study area.

Sericulture growers distribution on the basis of Level of Education

The sericulture growers were classified on the basis of Level of Education and the details are presented in Table 2. As per the availability of the data of sericulture growers, the level of education was classified into illiterate, Primary, Secondary, Higher Secondary, Graduate and Post Graduate and others. The grand total of district shows that it was having 80 sericulture growers in district of the study area.

adoption of innovative technologies, which are skilled basis for improving the cocoon production. Thus, in order to enhance the sericulture production there is scope to increase the percentage level of higher education.

Sericulture growers' distribution on the basis of Level of Occupation

Sericulture farmers distribution on the basis of level of occupation is presented in Table 3 indicates that the majority of the farmers were engaged in agricultural occupation i.e. 71 farmers out of 80 farmers followed by other types of occupation categories.

related to family size of the sample farmers were categorized into small (0-3 members), medium (4-5 members) and large (> 6 members).

The study revealed that in the Beed district, large per cent share were contributed by medium size of the family 58.75 per cent (47 sericulture growers) followed by large family size (>6 members) and small family size (0-3 members) contributing 30.00 per cent (24 sericulture growers) and 11.24 per cent (9 sericulture growers) to the total sample farmers, respectively.

The table provides an overview about majority of the farmers were belonged to medium size of family those were having 4-5 members followed by large and small family size which was having > 6 members and 0-3 members respectively. The family size contributes a great part in the silkworm rearing just because depending upon the family size farmers can rear up to 300 to 400 DFLs and even children also engaged in rearing activities during the rearing season of silkworm. As the number of brushed DFLs increased it will lead to increase in the cocoon production, ultimately it helps in increasing in the medium large size income as compared to small family size

income. Timely availability of family labour will help to address the problem of unavailability of skilled labour in acute situation of hired labour in agriculture.

Sericulture growers distribution on the basis of Land Holding

Sericulture growers distribution on the basis of land holding presented in Table 5. The data provides an insight into the land holding distribution of sericulture growers. The data pertaining to above table were classified into marginal (<1 ha.), small (1-2 ha.), medium (2-4 ha.), large (>4 ha.).

Table 5: Distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of land holding

Districts	Land Holding				Grand Total
	Marginal (<1 ha.)	Small (1-2 ha.)	Medium (2.01-4.00 ha.)	Large (>4ha.)	
Beed	15 (18.75)	52 (65.00)	10 (12.50)	3 (3.75)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

It was observed from the table that in the Beed district, the large number of farmers had small size of land holding (1-2 ha.) followed by marginal size (<1 ha.), medium size (2-4 ha.), and large size (>4 ha.) of land holding, contributing 65.00 per cent (52 Sericulture growers), 18.75 per cent (15 sericulture growers), 12.50 per cent (10 sericulture growers), 3.75 per cent (3 sericulture growers) to the total, respectively.

Sericulture growers' distribution on the basis of years of experience in sericulture

The distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of years of experience having the farmers in the sericulture production, is presented in Table 6. It is evident from the table that majority of the farmers were belonging to young group i.e. (0-5 years) followed by middle group (6-10 years) and old group (> 10 years) of years of experience.

Table 6: Distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of years of experience in sericulture

Districts	Years of experience in sericulture			Grand Total
	Less Experience (<5 years)	Medium Experience (6-10 years)	Long Experience (> 10 years)	
Beed	52 (65.00)	24 (30.00)	4 (5.00)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

It was ascertained from the table that the Beed district shows that out of 80 farmers most of the farmers 52 (65.00 per cent) sample farmers belonged to less experience category of years of experience followed by medium experience category and long experience category of experience having 24 farmers (30.00 per cent) and 4 sericulture growers (5.00 per cent) respectively. The reason behind increasing in adoption of sericulture as an enterprise that most of the farmers

pertaining to young and middle group were taken it as the family occupation.

Social Category wise distribution of Sericulture growers

The sericulture growers were categorized as per the social category viz., Scheduled Caste (SC), Scheduled Tribe (ST), Nomadic Tribe (NT), Other Backward Caste (OBC) and General is presented in Table 7. The social stratification were based on the caste distribution in India. (Yadav 2013).

Table 7: Social category wise classification of sericulture growers

Districts	Social Category wise distribution of Sericulture growers					Grand Total
	Scheduled Caste (SC)	Scheduled Tribe (ST)	Nomadic Tribe (NT)	Other Backward Caste (OBC)	General	
Beed	1 (1.25)	2 (2.50)	1 (1.25)	20 (25.00)	56 (70.00)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

The table 7 depicted that in the Beed district, the most of the of sericulture growers 56 (70.00 per cent) were general category followed by Other Backward Caste (OBC), Scheduled Tribe (ST), Scheduled Caste (SC) and Nomadic Tribe (NT) and were having 20 (25.00 per cent) sericulture growers, 2 (2.50 per cent) sericulture growers, 1 (1.25) sericulture growers, 1 (1.25) sericulture growers, respectively. The results of the study were in relevance with the findings of Yadav (2013). In India, the officially recognized social categories involves, Forward castes (FC), Other Backward Caste (OBC), Scheduled Tribe (ST), Scheduled Caste (SC) (Williams et.al., 2016).

Sericulture growers' classification according to their Family Type

The distribution of sericulture growers according to their family type is depicted in Table 8. The table shows that about 80 farmers of the total sample belonged to nuclear family whereas 11 farmers were having joint family. It was observed from the study that in the Beed district, the maximum per cent share were contributed by nuclear type of family 86.25 per cent (69 sericulture growers) followed by Joint family type 13.75 per cent (11 sericulture growers). The results of the study, were in accordance with result of Vishakantha (2018).

Table 8: Distribution of sericulture growers according to their family type

Districts	Family Type		Grand Total
	Nuclear	Joint	
Beed	69 (86.25)	11 (13.75)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

Sericulture growers distribution on the basis of Training Acquired

The distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of training acquired by the sericulture growers is shown in Table 9. It was observed from the study that in the Beed district, about 23 sericulture

growers had taken training (28.75 per cent) and large number of farmers i.e. 57 (71.25 per cent) have not taken any training. Thus large number of farmers have taken the training than the farmers having not acquired training.

Table 9: Distribution of sericulture growers on the basis of training acquired

Districts	Training		Grand Total
	Trained	Non Trained	
Beed	23 (28.75)	57 (71.25)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

Sericulture growers' distribution according to their Marital Status

Distribution of sericulture growers according to their marital status is presented in Table 10. The study revealed that, in the Beed district, about 79 (98.75 per cent) farmers were married and 1 (1.25 per cent)

farmer was unmarried. It could be seen from the table that, Number of married farmers are more as compared to unmarried farmers. The findings of the study were similar with the findings of Yadav (2013).

Table 10: Distribution of sericulture growers according to their marital status

Districts	Marital Status		Grand Total
	Married	Unmarried	
Beed	79 (98.75)	1 (1.25)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

Sericulture growers' distribution according to their house type

The data pertaining to house type was classified into Kachcha and Pucca type of house which is presented in Table 11.

Table 11: Distribution of sericulture growers according to their house type

Districts	House Type		Grand Total
	Kachcha	Pucca	
Beed	37 (46.25)	43 (53.75)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

It was ascertained from the study that in the Beed district, out of the total 80 farmers, 43 farmers (53.75 farmers) had pucca type of house on other side, 37 sericulture growers (46.25 farmers) had kachcha type of house. The results observed were similar in with results found by Yadav (2013) and Gaikwad *et.al.* 2022.

Sericulture growers' distribution according to their soil type

The distribution of sericulture growers according to their soil type is presented in Table 12. The data pertaining to soil type was categorized into Heavy, Medium and light.

Table 12: Distribution of sericulture growers according to their soil type

Districts	Soil Types			Grand Total
	Heavy	Medium	Light	
Beed	10 (12.50)	63 (78.75)	7 (8.75)	80 (100)

(Figures in parenthesis indicates percentages to total)

It was revealed from the study, that in the Beed district majority of farmers had taken plantation in Medium type of soil 63 (78.75 per cent) followed by heavy 10 (12.50 per cent) and light type of soil 7(8.75 per cent).

Information regarding variety of mulberry, cocoon species and sericulture training

The information regarding, variety of mulberry, cocoon species, source of training and training acquired by sericulture growers is presented in Table 13. In given study area all the farmers were using V1 variety of mulberry. In regard to species of cocoon they were

using CSR Double Hybrid cocoon species. In terms of source of training, from which farmers gained the training, out of 23 farmers, maximum number of farmers were acquired training from the government institutes 9 sericulture growers (39.13 per cent), followed by the progressive farmers 7 sericulture growers (30.43 per cent), Krishi Vigyan Kendra 4 sericulture growers (17.40 per cent), Mysore 2 sericulture growers (8.70 per cent) and Banglore 1 sericulture growers (4.34 per cent) whereas 57 farmers have not taken a training. All the sericulture growers have adopted mulberry as a main crop than the intercrop.

Table 13: Mulberry variety, cocoon species and sericulture training information

Sr. No.	Particulars	Frequency
1	Mulberry Variety (V1)	80 (100.00)
2	Cocoon Species (CSR Double Hybrid)	80 (100.00)
3	Source of Training	
	a. Progressive Farmers	7 (30.43)
	b. Krishi Vigyan Kendra	4 (17.40)
	c. Government	9 (39.13)
	d. Banglore	1 (4.34)
	e. Mysore	2 (8.70)
4.	Training acquired by farmers	
	a. Yes	23 (28.75)
	b. No	57 (71.25)

5	Adopted Mulberry as	
	Main Crop	80 (100.00)

(Figures in brackets indicates percentages to total)

Cropping pattern

Simply, cropping pattern is the production of area which is under various crops in different season by the sample farmers at a point of time of survey year. Cropping pattern influences the financial condition of the farmers.

Sr. No.	Particulars	Area (ha)	Percent
I	Kharif		
1	Soybean	0.34	16.04
2	kharif Bajari	0.04	2.07
3	Cotton	0.39	18.19
4	Pigeon pea (Tur)	0.02	0.83
5	Green gram/ black gram	0.14	6.50
6	Turmeric (ha)	0.00	0.00
	Sub total	0.93	
II	Rabi		
1	Rabi Jawar	0.24	11.08
2	Wheat	0.15	7.03
3	Chickpea	0.14	6.73
4	Onion	0.00	0.00
	Sub total	0.53	
III	Summer		
1	Groundnut	0.00	0.00
	Sub total	0.00	
IV	Annual		
1	Sugarcane	0.08	3.66
	Sub total	0.08	
V	Perennial		
1	Mulberry	0.62	29.30
2	Pomegranate	0.00	0.00
3	Orange	0.00	0.00
	Sub Total	0.62	
	Gross cropped area	2.15	100.00
	Net sown area	1.57	
	CI (%)		134.82

The cropping pattern of selected sericulture growers was calculated and presented in Table 14. In Beed district, the area under Kharif season was 0.93 ha. whereas, the area under cultivation in the Rabi season was 0.53 ha. and due to non-availability of water facility, the farmers have not cultivated groundnut in summer season. Among the various kharif crops, major area was occupied by Cotton crop i.e. 18.19 per cent to gross cropped area followed by Soybean (16.04 percent), Green gram/black gram (6.50 percent), Kharif Bajra (2.07 percent), Pigeon pea (Tur) (0.83 percent), and Turmeric (0.00 percent). In Rabi season the highest proportionate area was under Jawar which was 0.24 ha i.e. 11.08 per cent followed by Wheat (0.15 ha.), Chick pea (0.14 ha.). Sugarcane being an annual crop was grown as the cash crop and cultivated in an area of the 0.08 ha. It was resulted that, the gross cropped area was 2.15 ha. In regard to perennial crop the proportionate area under mulberry cultivation was 0.62 ha i.e. 29.30 per cent to gross cropped area. The net sown area was 1.57 ha with cropping intensity of 134.82 per cent on the selected sericulture farms.

The result revealed that the gross cropped area was 2.15 ha. In regard to perennial crop the proportionate area under mulberry cultivation was 0.62 ha i.e. 29.30 per cent to gross cropped area. The net sown area was 1.57 ha with cropping intensity of 134.82 per cent on the selected sericulture farm.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the study revealed that most of the sericulture growers were found to be of middle age group, married, had education up to secondary level, medium size of family, small farmers, belonged to general category, had nuclear family, kachcha type of house, growing

mulberry on medium type of soil, V1 variety of mulberry and CSR Double hybrid type of cocoon species. The proportionate area under mulberry cultivation was 0.62 ha i.e. 29.30 per cent to gross cropped area.

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